

On the F.Smarandache LCM function¹

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Abstract For any positive integer n , the famous F.Smarandache LCM function $SL(n)$ is defined as the smallest positive integer k such that $n \mid [1, 2, \dots, k]$, where $[1, 2, \dots, k]$ denotes the least common multiple of $1, 2, \dots, k$. The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary methods to study the value distribution properties of the function $SL(n)$, and give an interesting asymptotic formula for it.

Keywords F.Smarandache LCM function, value distribution, asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction

For any positive integer n , the famous F.Smarandache LCM function $SL(n)$ defined as the smallest positive integer k such that $n \mid [1, 2, \dots, k]$, where $[1, 2, \dots, k]$ denotes the least common multiple of $1, 2, \dots, k$. For example, the first few values of $SL(n)$ are $SL(1) = 1$, $SL(2) = 2$, $SL(3) = 3$, $SL(4) = 4$, $SL(5) = 5$, $SL(6) = 3$, $SL(7) = 7$, $SL(8) = 8$, $SL(9) = 9$, $SL(10) = 5$, $SL(11) = 11$, $SL(12) = 4$, $SL(13) = 13$, $SL(14) = 7$, $SL(15) = 5$, $SL(16) = 16$, $SL(17) = 17$, $SL(18) = 9$, $SL(20) = 5$, \dots . About the elementary properties of $SL(n)$, some authors had studied it, and obtained many interesting results, see reference [2], [3], [4] and [5]. For example, Murthy [2] showed that if n be a prime, then $SL(n) = S(n)$, where $S(n)$ denotes the Smarandache function, i.e., $S(n) = \min\{m : n \mid m!, m \in N\}$. Simultaneously, Murthy [2] also proposed the following problem:

$$SL(n) = S(n), \quad S(n) \neq n? \quad (1)$$

Le Maohua [3] completely solved this problem, and proved the following conclusion:

Every positive integer n satisfying (1) can be expressed as

$$n = 12 \quad \text{or} \quad n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r} p,$$

where p_1, p_2, \dots, p_r, p are distinct primes, and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_r$ are positive integers satisfying $p > p_i^{\alpha_i}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$.

Lv Zhongtian [4] studied the mean value properties of $SL(n)$, and proved that for any fixed positive integer k and any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

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$$\sum_{n \leq x} SL(n) = \frac{\pi^2}{12} \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{c_i \cdot x^2}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where c_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

Ge Jian [5] studied the value distribution of $[SL(n) - S(n)]^2$, and proved that

$$\sum_{n \leq x} [SL(n) - S(n)]^2 = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \zeta\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) \cdot x^{\frac{3}{2}} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{c_i}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta-function, c_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) are constants. The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary methods to study the value distribution properties of $SL(n)$, and prove an interesting asymptotic formula. That is, we shall prove the following conclusion:

Theorem. For any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in N \\ SL(n) \leq x}} 1 = 2^{\frac{x}{\ln x} [1 + O(\frac{\ln \ln x}{\ln x})]},$$

where N denotes the set of all positive integers.

From this Theorem we may immediately deduce the following:

Corollary. For any real number $x > 1$, let $\pi(x)$ denotes the number of all primes $p \leq x$, then we have the limit formula

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \left[\sum_{\substack{n \in N \\ SL(n) \leq x}} 1 \right]^{\frac{1}{\pi(x)}} = 2.$$

§2. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall prove our theorem directly. Let x be any real number with $x > 2$, then for any prime $p \leq x$, there exists one and only one positive integer $\alpha(p)$ such that

$$p^{\alpha(p)} \leq x < p^{\alpha(p)+1}.$$

From the properties of $SL(n)$ and [2] we know that if $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_k^{\alpha_k}$ be the factorization of n into primes powers, then

$$SL(n) = \max\{p_1^{\alpha_1}, p_2^{\alpha_2}, \dots, p_r^{\alpha_r}\}. \quad (2)$$

Let $m = \prod_{p \leq x} p^{\alpha(p)}$. Then for any integer $d|m$, we have $SL(d) \leq x$. For any positive integers u and v with $(u, v) = 1$, if $SL(u) \leq x$, $SL(v) \leq x$, then $SL(uv) \leq x$. On the other hand, for any $SL(n) \leq x$, from the definition of $SL(n)$ we also have $n|m$. So from these and the properties of the Dirichlet divisor function $d(n)$ we have

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in N \\ SL(n) \leq x}} 1 = \sum_{d|m} 1 = \prod_{p \leq x} (1 + \alpha(p)) = e^{\sum_{p \leq x} \ln(1 + \alpha(p))}. \quad (3)$$

From the definition of $\alpha(p)$ we have $\alpha(p) \leq \frac{\ln x}{\ln p} < \alpha(p) + 1$ or

$$\alpha(p) = \left\lfloor \frac{\ln x}{\ln p} \right\rfloor. \quad (4)$$

Therefore, from (4) we may immediately get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{p \leq x} \ln(1 + \alpha(p)) &= \sum_{p \leq x} \ln \left(1 + \left\lfloor \frac{\ln x}{\ln p} \right\rfloor \right) \\ &= \sum_{p \leq \frac{x}{\ln^2 x}} \ln \left(1 + \left\lfloor \frac{\ln x}{\ln p} \right\rfloor \right) + \sum_{\frac{x}{\ln^2 x} < p \leq x} \ln \left(1 + \left\lfloor \frac{\ln x}{\ln p} \right\rfloor \right). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Now we estimate each term in (5). It is clear that

$$\sum_{p \leq \frac{x}{\ln^2 x}} \ln \left(1 + \left\lfloor \frac{\ln x}{\ln p} \right\rfloor \right) \ll \sum_{p \leq \frac{x}{\ln^2 x}} \ln \ln x \ll \frac{x \ln \ln x}{\ln^3 x}. \quad (6)$$

If $\frac{x}{\ln^2 x} < p \leq x$, then $1 \leq \frac{\ln x}{\ln p} < 1 + \frac{2 \ln \ln x}{\ln x - 2 \ln \ln x}$. So from the famous Prime Theorem

$$\pi(x) = \frac{x}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^2 x}\right)$$

and

$$\ln(1 + y) \sim y, \quad \text{as } y \rightarrow 0,$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\frac{x}{\ln^2 x} < p \leq x} \ln \left(1 + \left\lfloor \frac{\ln x}{\ln p} \right\rfloor \right) &= \sum_{\frac{x}{\ln^2 x} < p \leq x} \ln 2 + O\left(\sum_{\frac{x}{\ln^2 x} < p \leq x} \frac{\ln \ln x}{\ln x}\right) \\ &= \ln 2 \cdot \frac{x}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x \ln \ln x}{\ln^2 x}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Combining (3), (5), (6) and (7) we may immediately obtain

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in N \\ SL(n) \leq x}} 1 = 2^{\frac{x}{\ln x} [1 + O(\frac{\ln \ln x}{\ln x})]},$$

where N denotes the set of all positive integers. This completes the proof of Theorem.

The corollary follows from

$$\left[\sum_{\substack{n \in N \\ SL(n) \leq x}} 1 \right]^{\frac{1}{\pi(x)}} = 2^{1+O\left(\frac{\ln \ln x}{\ln x}\right)} = 2 + O\left(\frac{\ln \ln x}{\ln x}\right)$$

as $x \rightarrow \infty$.

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